

Machine learning discoveries of FOXM1-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells

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Abstract

Forkhead box protein M1 (FOXM1) belongs to the family of transcription factors Forkhead box (FOX). Forkhead box is a sequence of 80 to 100 amino acids forming a motif that binds to DNA. It is also known as the winged helix due to the butterfly-like appearance of the loops in the protein structure of the domain. FOXM1 stimulates proliferation by promoting S-phase entry and M-phase entry and is also involved in proper execution of mitosis. Further, it is implicated in tumorigenesis and causes both tumor initiation and progression. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, FOXM1 was found to be down regulated along with other genes. A recently developed search engine ranked combinations of FOXM1-X (X, a particular gene/protein) at 2nd order level after drug administration. Some of these combinations have been tested in wet lab, however many have been pointed out by the search engine that are yet to be explored/tested. These rankings reveal which FOXM1-X combinations might be working synergistically in CRC. In this research work, I cover combinations of FOXM1 with members of OTU deubiquitinase (OTUD), telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT), RAD9-HUS1-RAD1 interacting nuclear orphan 1 (RHNO1), stathmin 1/oncoprotein 18 (STMN1), Wnt family member (WNT), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), Never in mitosis gene A (NIMA)-related kinase 2 (NEK2), serine peptidase inhibitor Kazal type (SPINK), ATP binding cassette subfamily (ABC), alkB alkylation repair homolog (ALKBH), Rho GTPase activating proteins (ARHGAP), ASF1 anti-silencing function histone chaperone (ASF1), peroxiredoxin (PRDX), aurora kinase (AURK), cluster of differentiation/designation molecules (CD), cell division cycle (CDC), cell division cycle associated (CDCA), E2F transcription factor (E2F), cyclin dependent kinase (CDK), centromere protein (CENP), cytoskeleton associated protein (CKAP), DEAD-box helicase (DDX), maternal embryonic leucine zipper kinase (MELK), DEP domain containing (DEPDC), ERCC excision repair (ERCC), family with sequence similarity (FAM), Fanconi anemia complementation group (FANC), frizzled class receptor (FZD), high mobility group (HMG),

*ML discoveries of FOXM1-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated CRC cells

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heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein (HNRNP), heat shock protein family (HSP), kinesin family member (KIF), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA (LINC), methyltransferase (METTL), mitochondrial ribosomal protein L (MRPL), polo like kinase (PLK), DNA polymerase (POL), DNA-dependent/directed RNA polymerase (POLR), SCL/TAL1 interrupting locus (STIL), splicing factor 3 (SF3), ubiquitin specific peptidase (USP), integrin subunit (ITG), Zinc fingers C2H2-type family member (ZIC) and ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 (UBE2) family.

Keywords: FOXM1, Porcupine inhibitor ETC-1922159, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning, Colorectal cancer.

1. Introduction

1.1. FOXM1

Ye et al. [1] showed that hepatocyte nuclear factor $3\alpha/\beta$ (HNF- $3\alpha/\beta$) proteins had homology in the winged helix/fork head DNA binding domain and regulated cell-specific transcription in hepatocytes, and respiratory and intestinal epithelia. They described two isoforms of the winged helix transcription factor family, HNF-3/fork head homolog 11-A/B (HFH-11-A/B), isolated from the human colon carcinoma cell lines which were expressed in embryonic mesenchymal and epithelial cells and its expression was reactivated in adult cell types by proliferative signals or oxidative stress. Castaneda et al. [2] provide a review on the roles of many FOX family members in epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), hormone signaling, drug resistance, metabolism, immune system regulation, cancer development and progression and their functions as pioneering factors.

Wierstra and Alves [3] indicate that FOXM1 is a transcription factor that regulates genes controlling G1/S-transition, S-phase progression, G2/M-transition and M-phase progression. Invariably, both its expression and activity, are antagonistically regulated by many (anti- &) proliferation signals. Yang et al. [4] found that FOXM1 bound to and stimulated the promoter of Slug leading to EMT progression in human breast cancer. Francis et al. [5] observed that tyrosine kinase receptor HER2 receptor regulates the expression of the FOXM1 transcription factor, in breast cancer development. In prostate cancer cells, results by Liu et al. [6] provided new evidence for the regulatory mechanism of aberrant CDC6 oncogene transcription by FOXM1 and AR. In the study of pancreatic cancer metabolism, Cui et al. [7] found that FOXM1 regulates aerobic glycolysis (or Warburg effect, that is a shift from oxidative phosphorylation to glycolysis) by changing the expression of lactate dehydrogenase A (LDHA). This lead to elevated LDH activity, lactate production, and glucose utilization, thus causing cancer cell growth and metastasis. In gastric cancer cells, Zeng et al. [8] observed that FOXM1 was over-expressed and its inhibition prompted p53- and p16- independent senescence of cancer cells by regulating the expression of p27^{kip1} and other targets. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, FOXM1 was found to be down regulated along with other genes. Some combinations of FOXM1 have been confirmed in wet lab, however, many of the combinations have not been explored/tested or

are known. To reveal these combinations, I use a modification of a recently published machine learning based search engine, details of which are given in the next section.

1.2. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [9], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Readers are requested to go through the adaptation of the above mentioned work for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159, Sinha [10]. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [11] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations.

2. Results & Discussion

2.1. FOXM1 related synergies

2.1.1. FOXM1 - OTUD6B / TERT / RHNO1 / STMN1 / WNT10B / TPX2 / NEK2 / SPINK4

In breast cancer cells Wang et al. [12] revealed that OTUD7B interacted with and deubiquitinated FOXM1, leading to its stabilization. This stabilization led to proliferation. They also showed that knocking down OTUD7B inhibited the proliferation and stemness of breast cancer cells by enhancing FOXM1 degradation. In gastric cancer, Tang et al. [13] found that FOXM1 interrupted the interaction between the E3 ligase MKRN1 and hTERT and decreased the protein degradation of the latter. Further studies revealed that FOXM1 interacted with hTERT through its DNA-binding domain (DBD) region. hTERT is the core subunit of telomerase that facilitates cancer initiation and progression by maintaining cell immortalization, promoting cell proliferation and inhibiting cell apoptosis. They found that hTERT played important roles in FOXM1-mediated activation of the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway to promote gastric cancer cell proliferation. Thus they found a novel non-classical function of FOXM1 to increase hTERT protein stability. In high-grade serous carcinoma (HGSC), Barger et al. [14] showed that FOXM1 and RHNO1 are bidirectional genes (BDG) that are co-regulated by a bidirectional promoter (BDP) (named F/R-BDP). FOXM1 and RHNO1 each promoted oncogenic phenotypes in HGSC cells, that included clonogenic growth, DNA homologous recombination repair, and poly-ADP ribosylase inhibitor resistance. STMN1 is a microtubule-binding protein which inhibits the assembly of microtubule dimer or promotes the depolymerization of microtubules. It was reported as a major responsive factor of paclitaxel resistance for clinical chemotherapy of tumor patients. Liu et al. [15] suggest that FOXM1 promotes cell proliferation by upregulating STMN1 axis and contributes to tumorigenesis in gastric cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma and colorectal cancer. In cultured renal tubular epithelial cells, Xie et al. [16] found that over-expression of FOXM1 promoted 8 Wnts expression, while knock-down on FOXM1-suppressed multi-Wnts including WNT1, WNT2b and WNT3 expression induced by

Ang II. Their findings show that FOXM1 regulated multi-Wnt family members leading to renal fibrosis. In hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), Wang et al. [17] showed that FOXM1 bound to the TPX2 promoter, and regulated TPX2 activity to drive proliferation. In esophageal squamous cell carcinoma (ESCC) tissues, Li et al. [18] found that NEK2 was upregulated and FOXM1 was identified as its downstream target in the regulation of ESCC. Their mechanistic studies indicated that NEK2 may promote the malignant progression of ESCC by inhibiting cellular senescence through the activation of the FOXM1/c-Myc/p27 signaling pathways. Ding et al. [19] found that FOXM1 directly promotes SPINK1 transcription, enhancing tumor cell proliferation and metastasis in liver cancer, while regulating the p53 pathway. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these individual members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these individual members along with FOXM1.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of these individual members w.r.t FOXM1. TERT - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 385 (laplace), 318 (linear) and 381 (rbf). RHNO1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 731 (linear) and 1564 (rbf). STMN1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 168 (laplace), 284 (linear) and 221 (rbf). WNT10B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1020 (laplace), 1313 (linear) and 560 (rbf). TPX2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 771 (laplace), 45 (linear) and 286 (rbf). NEK2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 492 (laplace), 144 (linear) and 350 (rbf). SPINK4 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 972 (laplace) and 1042 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, OTUD6B showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • individual members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > TERT / RHNO1 / STMN1 / WNT10B / TPX2 / NEK2 / SPINK4.

2.1.2. FOXM1 - ABC

Paclitaxel is clinically used as a chemotherapeutic administration for several cancer types, but acquired drug resistance results in the failure of therapy, metastasis and relapse. The drug efflux mediated by ABC transporters and the survival signals activated by FOX molecules are influential in the development of paclitaxel drug resistance. Hou et al. [20] developed several types of paclitaxel-resistant (TR) nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) cells which acquired cancer stem cell (CSC) phenotypes and underwent EMT, and developed multidrug resistance. They found that FOXM1 and ABCC5 were overexpressed in the TR NPC cells and patient tumor tissues as FOXM1 regulated ABCC5 gene transcription by binding to the FHK consensus motifs at the promoter region. Similar results were reported in cervical cancer cells by Hou et al. [21] and He et al. [22]. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
OTUD6B - FOXM1	1706	1660	1389
TERT - FOXM1	385	318	381
RHNO1 - FOXM1	1874	731	1564
STMN1 - FOXM1	168	284	221
WNT10B - FOXM1	1020	1313	560
TPX2 - FOXM1	771	45	286
NEK2 - FOXM1	492	144	350
SPINK4 - FOXM1	972	2225	1042

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t FOXM1	
TERT	FOXM1
RHNO1	FOXM1
STMN1	FOXM1
WNT10B	FOXM1
TPX2	FOXM1
NEK2	FOXM1
SPINK4	FOXM1

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and individual members.

1922159, these ABC members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these ABC members along with FOXM1.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of ABC members w.r.t FOXM1. ABCE1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 464 (laplace), 493 (linear) and 885 (rbf). ABCA2 - FOXM1 shows

low ranking of 1019 (laplace), 1079 (linear) and 946 (rbf). ABCF2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1531 (laplace) and 1432 (linear). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING ABC MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF ABC MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ABCE1 - FOXM1	464	493	885
ABCA2 - FOXM1	1019	1079	946
ABCF2 - FOXM1	1531	1432	2056

Table 3: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS ABC members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • ABC members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 \rightarrow ABC-E1/A2/F2.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ABC members w.r.t FOXM1	
ABC-E1/A2/F2	FOXM1

Table 4: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and ABC members.

2.1.3. FOXM1 - ALKBH

In ovarian cancer (OV) cells, results by Li et al. [23] showed that ALKBH5 directly regulated the m⁶A modification and stability of PVT1 which further led to regulation of FOXM1, thus affecting malignant behaviours and chemosensitivity. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ALKBH members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these ALKBH members along with FOXM1.

Table 5 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 6 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 5. The table 5 shows rankings of ALKBH members w.r.t FOXM1. ALKBH2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1081 (laplace), 803 (linear) and 561 (rbf). ALKBH8 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 770 (linear) and 1347 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy

existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, ALKBH4 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING ALKBH MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF ALKBH MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ALKBH2 - FOXM1	1081	803	561
ALKBH8 - FOXM1	1648	770	1347
ALKBH4 - FOXM1	2285	2575	2568

Table 5: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS ALKBH members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 5 graphically, with the following influences - • ALKBH members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > ALKBH-2/8.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ALKBH members w.r.t FOXM1	
ALKBH-2/8	FOXM1

Table 6: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and ALKBH members.

2.1.4. FOXM1 - ARHGAP

ARHGAP11A can facilitate GTP hydrolysis in RhoA and is transcriptionally activated by FOXM1 via multiple FOXM1 binding sites in the promoter regions in tongue squamous cell carcinoma (TSCC) cells, as shown by Zhang et al. [24]. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ARHGAP members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these ARHGAP members along with FOXM1.

Table 7 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 8 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 7. The table 7 shows rankings of ARHGAP members w.r.t FOXM1. ARHGAP11A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 36 (laplace), 123 (linear) and 12 (rbf). ARHGAP11B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 499 (laplace), 36 (linear) and 54 (rbf). ARHGAP33 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1013 (laplace), 1036 (linear) and 354 (rbf). These rankings point

to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, ARHGAP19 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING ARHGAP MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF ARHGAP MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ARHGAP11A - FOXM1	36	123	12
ARHGAP11B - FOXM1	499	36	54
ARHGAP33 - FOXM1	1013	1036	354
ARHGAP19 - FOXM1	2519	1627	1846

Table 7: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS ARHGAP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 7 graphically, with the following influences - • ARHGAP members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > ARHGAP-11A/11B/33.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ARHGAP members w.r.t FOXM1	
ARHGAP-11A/11B/33	FOXM1

Table 8: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and ARHGAP members.

2.1.5. FOXM1 - ASF/PRDX

In gastric cancer (GC), Zhao et al. [25] showed that FOXM1 transcriptionally activates ASF1B and the latter is a downstream effector of FOXM1-mediated progression. Further this proliferation and maintenance of oxidative stress homeostasis in GC happens via ASF1B-induced downstream PRDX3 expression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ASF1-PRDX members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these ASF1-PRDX members along with FOXM1.

Table 9 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 10 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 9. The table 9 shows rankings of ASF-PRDX members w.r.t FOXM1. ASF1B - FOXM1

shows low ranking of 569 (laplace), 404 (linear) and 663 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, ASF1A, PRDX3, PRDX4, PRDX2 and PRDX6 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment. With respect to the above reference in gastric cancer, ASF1 and PRDX3 did not show synergistic role in CRC before treatment, as pointed out by the high rank in CRC treated with ETC-1922159.

RANKING ASF1-PRDX MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF ASF1-PRDX MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ASF1B - FOXM1	569	404	663
ASF1A - FOXM1	1728	2294	1945
PRDX3 - FOXM1	1730	1943	1603
PRDX4 - FOXM1	1958	1339	2363
PRDX2 - FOXM1	2230	2505	1886
PRDX6 - FOXM1	2622	1790	2567

Table 9: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS ASF1-PRDX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 9 graphically, with the following influences - • ASF1-PRDX members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > ASF1-B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ASF1-PRDX members w.r.t FOXM1	
ASF1-B	FOXM1

Table 10: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and ASF1-PRDX members.

2.1.6. FOXM1 - AURK

In a review, Chen et al. [26] indicate that AURKA can function in either the cytoplasm or the nucleus and regulates basic cellular processes. This regulation happens via the phosphorylation of downstream substrates and AURKA can promote the transcription and expression of oncogenes together with other transcription factors in the nucleus like FOXM1. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between

the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these AURK members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these AURK members along with FOXM1.

Table 11 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 12 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 11. The table 11 shows rankings of AURK members w.r.t FOXM1. AURKA - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 575 (laplace), 344 (linear) and 45 (rbf). AURKB - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 119 (laplace), 33 (linear) and 284 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING AURK MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF AURK MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
AURKA - FOXM1	575	344	45
AURKB - FOXM1	119	33	284

Table 11: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS AURK members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 11 graphically, with the following influences - • AURK members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 \rightarrow AURK-A/B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
AURK members w.r.t FOXM1	
AURK-A/B	FOXM1

Table 12: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and AURK members.

2.1.7. FOXM1 - CD

Wuputra et al. [27] showed that FOXM1 directly upregulated CD44 expression and triggered stem cell features, to enhance the progression of human liver cancer and survival. They found upregulation of FOXM1 and CD44 in the HepG2.Rego.R cells, indicating that FOXM1 seemed to be involved in drug resistance. Additionally, FOXM1 knockdown impaired the expression of CD44 and SOX2 as well as cell proliferation and sphere formation as CSC features in regorafenib-resistant cells. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these CD members,

and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these CD members along with FOXM1.

Table 13 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 14 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 13. The table 13 shows rankings of CD members w.r.t FOXM1. CD19 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 150 (laplace), 310 (linear) and 88 (rbf). CD6 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 208 (laplace), 392 (linear) and 492 (rbf). CD200 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 622 (laplace), 269 (linear) and 588 (rbf). CD83 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 767 (laplace), 354 (linear) and 748 (rbf). CD37 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 890 (laplace) and 1068 (linear) CD320 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1421 (laplace), 1451 (linear) and 1348 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CD27, CD44 and CD302 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment. With respect to the above reference, CD44 did not show synergistic role in CRC before treatment, as pointed out by the high rank in CRC treated with ETC-1922159.

RANKING CD MEMBERS VS FOXM1

RANKING OF CD MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1	laplace	linear	rbf
CD19 - FOXM1	150	310	88
CD6 - FOXM1	208	392	492
CD200 - FOXM1	622	269	588
CD83 - FOXM1	767	354	748
CD37 - FOXM1	890	1068	1877
CD320 - FOXM1	1421	1451	1348
CD27 - FOXM1	1642	1376	2406
CD44 - FOXM1	2531	815	2004
CD302 - FOXM1	2591	2400	1871

Table 13: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS CD members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 13 graphically, with the following influences - • CD members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > CD-19/6/200/83/37/320.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

CD members w.r.t FOXM1

CD-19/6/200/83/37/320 FOXM1

Table 14: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and CD members.

2.1.8. FOXM1 - CDC

Pal-Ghosh et al. [28] showed that CDC2 expression is sharply increased in pulmonary artery smooth muscle cells from patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) in comparison to normal PASMC cells. The expression of CDC2 was coordinated with increased expression of FOXM1 and PLK1 so that strong growth of the cells within the pulmonary artery was assured. These pathways contribute to vascular smooth muscle cells from patients (HPASMC) hyperplasticity in PAH. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these CDC members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these CDC members along with FOXM1.

Table 15 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 16 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 15. The table 15 shows rankings of CDC members w.r.t FOXM1. CDC25C - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 29 (laplace), 34 (linear) and 10 (rbf). CDC20 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 120 (laplace), 48 (linear) and 185 (rbf). CDC45 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 195 (laplace), 68 (linear) and 11 (rbf). CDC7 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 206 (laplace), 181 (linear) and 76 (rbf). CDC25A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 739 (laplace), 423 (linear) and 431 (rbf). CDC6 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 759 (laplace), 1553 (linear) and 1137 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CDC123 and CDC23 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 15 graphically, with the following influences - • CDC members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > CDC-/25C/20/45/7/25A/6.

2.1.9. FOXM1 - CDCA/E2F

In breast cancer cells Xiong et al. [29] showed that CDCA5 was upregulated in breast cancer and its knockdown inhibited proliferation and migration in vitro. Malignant behaviours were caused by CDCA5 via promoting the binding of E2F1 to FOXM1 promoter. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these CDCA-E2F members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these CDCA-E2F members along with FOXM1.

RANKING CDC MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF CDC MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CDC25C - FOXM1	29	34	10
CDC20 - FOXM1	120	48	185
CDC45 - FOXM1	195	68	11
CDC7 - FOXM1	206	181	76
CDC25A - FOXM1	739	423	431
CDC6 - FOXM1	759	1553	1137
CDC123 - FOXM1	2346	2268	2620
CDC23 - FOXM1	2418	2667	2470

Table 15: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS CDC members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
CDC members w.r.t FOXM1	
CDC-/25C/20/45/7/25A/6	FOXM1

Table 16: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and CDC members.

Table 17 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 18 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 17. The table 17 shows rankings of CDCA-E2F members w.r.t FOXM1. CDCA5 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 19 (laplace), 104 (linear) and 58 (rbf). CDCA2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 156 (laplace), 175 (linear) and 182 (rbf). CDCA7L - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 177 (laplace), 232 (linear) and 252 (rbf). CDCA4 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 692 (laplace), 1021 (linear) and 574 (rbf). CDCA7 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1032 (laplace), 12 (linear) and 406 (rbf). CDCA8 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1261 (laplace), 632 (linear) and 1446 (rbf). E2F8 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 284 (laplace), 226 (linear) and 272 (rbf). E2F2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 297 (laplace), 502 (linear) and 301 (rbf). E2F1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 750 (laplace), 619 (linear) and 375 (rbf). E2F7 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1326 (laplace), 448 (linear) and 259 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CDCA3 and E2F5 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING CDCA-E2F MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF CDCA-E2F MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CDCA5 - FOXM1	19	104	58
CDCA2 - FOXM1	156	175	182
CDCA7L - FOXM1	177	232	252
CDCA4 - FOXM1	692	1021	574
CDCA7 - FOXM1	1032	12	406
CDCA8 - FOXM1	1261	632	1446
CDCA3 - FOXM1	2647	1673	1748
E2F8 - FOXM1	284	226	272
E2F2 - FOXM1	297	502	301
E2F1 - FOXM1	750	619	375
E2F7 - FOXM1	1326	448	259
E2F5 - FOXM1	2505	1840	1610

Table 17: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS CDCA-E2F members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 17 graphically, with the following influences - • CDCA members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > CDCA-5/2/7L/4/7/8 and • E2F members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > E2F-8/2/1/7.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
CDCA-E2F members w.r.t FOXM1	
CDCA-5/2/7L/4/7/8	FOXM1
E2F-8/2/1/7	FOXM1

Table 18: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and CDCA-E2F members.

2.1.10. FOXM1 - CDK

FOXM1 is one of the main players in the network governing self-renewal in epidermal stem cells (EPSCs). Polito et al. [30] identified CDK1 as the kinase controlling FOXM1 activity in human primary keratinocytes. CDK1 phosphorylated FOXM1 at specific residues, thus stabilizing the protein and enhancing its nuclear localization and transcriptional activity, promoting self-renewal. Further, FOXM1 bound to the CDK1 promoter, leading to its expression. Thus the feedforward loop helps in maintaining self-renewal in EPSCs. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these CDK members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these CDK members along with FOXM1.

Table 19 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 20 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 19. The table 19 shows rankings of CDK members w.r.t FOXM1. CDK1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 142 (laplace), 131 (linear) and 181 (rbf). CDK20 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 811 (laplace), 874 (linear) and 1009 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CDK6 and CDK4 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING CDK MEMBERS VS FOXM1

RANKING OF CDK MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CDK1 - FOXM1	142	131	181
CDK20 - FOXM1	811	874	1009
CDK6 - FOXM1	2065	2538	2492
CDK4 - FOXM1	2354	2241	2022

Table 19: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS CDK members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 19 graphically, with the following influences - • CDK members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 \rightarrow CDK-1/20.

2.1.11. FOXM1 - CENP

Shen et al. [31] found that YTHDC1 promoted FOXM1 expression in a m^6A modification manner. Further, FOXM1 regulated cell growth, metastasis, and glycolysis through binding with CENPA promoter in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) tis-

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

CDK members w.r.t FOXM1

CDK-1/20

FOXM1

Table 20: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and CDK members.

sues. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these CENP members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these CENP members along with FOXM1.

Table 21 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 22 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 21. The table 21 shows rankings of CENP members w.r.t FOXM1. CENPH - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 49 (laplace), 223 (linear) and 48 (rbf). CENPU - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 225 (laplace), 145 (linear) and 80 (rbf). CENPA - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 245 (laplace), 113 (linear) and 174 (rbf). CENPE - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 257 (laplace), 88 (linear) and 59 (rbf). CENPF - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 342 (laplace), 227 (linear) and 57 (rbf). CENPJ - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 435 (laplace), 585 (linear) and 74 (rbf). CENPM - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 463 (laplace), 240 (linear) and 868 (rbf). CENPL - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 478 (laplace) and 948 (rbf). CENPN - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 511 (laplace), 856 (linear) and 1378 (rbf). CENPW - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 531 (laplace), 725 (linear) and 445 (rbf). CENPK - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 612 (laplace), 116 (linear) and 573 (rbf). CENPI - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 920 (laplace), 491 (linear) and 563 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CENPO and CENPV showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING CENP MEMBERS VS FOXM1								
RANKING OF CENP MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1								
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
CENPH - FOXM1	49	223	48	CENPU - FOXM1	225	145	80	
CENPA - FOXM1	245	113	174	CENPE - FOXM1	257	88	59	
CENPF - FOXM1	342	227	57	CENPJ - FOXM1	435	585	74	
CENPM - FOXM1	463	240	868	CENPL - FOXM1	478	1758	948	
CENPN - FOXM1	511	856	1378	CENPW - FOXM1	531	725	445	
CENPK - FOXM1	612	116	573	CENPI - FOXM1	920	491	563	
CENPO - FOXM1	1968	1694	2003	CENPV - FOXM1	2293	2638	1030	

Table 21: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS CENP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 21 graphically, with the following influences - • CENP members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > CENP-H/U/A/E/F/J/M/L/N/W/K/I.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

CENP members w.r.t FOXM1
CENP-H/U/A/E/F/J/M/L/N/W/K/I FOXM1

Table 22: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and CENP members.

2.1.12. FOXM1 - CKAP

CKAP4 has been reported as an important regulator of glioblastoma (GBM). Xu et al. [32] demonstrated that CKAP4 knockdown remarkably reduced the malignant potential of GBM cells, whereas its overexpression had the reverse effects. Further they showed that overexpression of CKAP4 led to increased FOXM1 expression in union with an increased level of AKT and ERK phosphorylation. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these CKAP members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these CKAP members along with FOXM1.

Table 23 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 24 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 23. The table 23 shows rankings of CKAP members w.r.t FOXM1. CKAP2L - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 280 (laplace), 275 (linear) and 363 (rbf). CKAP2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 536 (laplace), 251 (linear) and 191 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CKAP5 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING CKAP MEMBERS VS FOXM1

RANKING OF CKAP MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1

	laplace	linear	rbf
CKAP2L - FOXM1	280	275	363
CKAP2 - FOXM1	536	251	191
CKAP5 - FOXM1	1836	2446	2633

Table 23: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS CKAP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 23 graphically, with the following influences - • CKAP members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > CKAP-2/2L.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

CKAP members w.r.t FOXM1	
CKAP-2/2L	FOXM1

Table 24: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and CKAP members.

2.1.13. FOXM1 - DDX

In ovarian cancer (OC) cells, Zhao et al. [33] determined that DDX23 was upregulated and by functional assays showed that DDX23 silencing impeded cell proliferation/invasion in vitro and tumor growth in vivo. They observed that DDX23 regulated the mRNA processing of FOXM1 and its silencing reduced the production of FOXM1C, an oncogenic transcript of FOXM1 in OC, thereby decreasing the FOXM1 protein expression and attenuating the malignant progression of OC. Similarly, in hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) Li et al. [34] found DDX56 was found to be overexpressed, lead to tumor cell proliferation, migration, invasion, EMT, and stemness. They also showed that MELK mediated FOXM1 expression, thus regulating cancer stemness and malignant traits. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these DDX members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these DDX members along with FOXM1.

Table 25 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 26 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 25. The table 25 shows rankings of DDX members w.r.t FOXM1. DDX20 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 154 (laplace), 1370 (linear) and 1419 (rbf). DDX12P - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 296 (laplace), 347 (linear) and 207 (rbf). DDX28 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 665 (laplace), 677 (linear) and 1980 DDX10 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1048 (laplace), 494 (linear) and 377 (rbf). DDX31 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1086 (laplace), 1463 (linear) and 971 (rbf). DDX21 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1272 (laplace) and 1116 (rbf). DDX55 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1287 (laplace), 915 (linear) and 1440 (rbf). DDX11 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1289 (laplace), 1775 and 875 (rbf). DDX51 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1307 (linear) and 1070 (rbf). MELK - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 961 (laplace), 461 (linear) and 237 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, DDX19A, DDX56, DDX46, DDX18, DDX27 and DDX54 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 25 graphically, with the following influences - • DDX members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > DDX-20/12P/28/10/31/21/55/11/51

RANKING DDX MEMBERS VS FOXM1							
RANKING OF DDX MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
DDX20 - FOXM1	154	1370	1419	DDX12P - FOXM1	296	347	207
DDX28 - FOXM1	665	677	1980	DDX10 - FOXM1	1048	494	377
DDX31 - FOXM1	1086	1463	971	DDX21 - FOXM1	1272	2005	1116
DDX55 - FOXM1	1287	915	1440	DDX11 - FOXM1	1289	1775	875
DDX51 - FOXM1	1629	1307	1070	DDX19A - FOXM1	1734	2126	1535
DDX56 - FOXM1	2363	2203	2269	DDX46 - FOXM1	2471	2149	2368
DDX18 - FOXM1	2523	1929	1585	DDX27 - FOXM1	2565	2055	2737
DDX54 - FOXM1	2608	2144	2528				
MELK - FOXM1	961	461	237				

Table 25: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS DDX members.

and • MELK members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > MELK.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
DDX members w.r.t FOXM1	
DDX-20/12P/28/10/31/21/55/11/51	FOXM1
MELK	FOXM1

Table 26: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and DDX members.

2.1.14. FOXM1 - DEPDC

Qiu et al. [35] identified elevated DEPDC1 expression in oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC). Additionally, FOXM1 interacted with DEPDC1, thus facilitating Wnt/ β -catenin signal transduction and β -catenin protein nuclear expression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these DEPDC members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these DEPDC members along with FOXM1.

Table 27 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 28 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 27. The table 27 shows rankings of DEPDC members w.r.t FOXM1. DEPDC4 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 292 (laplace), 445 (linear) and 761 (rbf). DEPDC1B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 397 (laplace), 224 (linear) and 106 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, DEPDC7 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING DEPDC MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF DEPDC MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
DEPDC4 - FOXM1	292	445	761
DEPDC1B - FOXM1	397	224	106
DEPDC7 - FOXM1	2138	1936	1920

Table 27: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS DEPDC members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 27 graphically, with the following influences - • DEPDC members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > DEPDC-4/1B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
DEPDC members w.r.t FOXM1	
DEPDC-4/1B	FOXM1

Table 28: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and DEPDC members.

2.1.15. FOXM1 - ERCC

In laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma (LSCC), Cui et al. [36] revealed that ERCC6L expression was elevated and ERCC6L knockdown LSCC cells showed decreased proliferation and migration, increased apoptosis, and reactive oxygen species (ROS). Further, they showed that overexpression of ERCC6L caused nuclear translocation of FOXM1 to facilitate direct binding to the KIF4A promoter and upregulated KIF4A expression which lead to progression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ERCC members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these ERCC members along with FOXM1.

Table 29 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 30 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 29. The table 29 shows rankings of ERCC members w.r.t FOXM1. ERCC6L - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 153 (laplace), 82 (linear) and 193 (rbf). ERCC8 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 870 (laplace), 1189 (linear) and 912 (rbf). These rankings point to the

synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING ERCC MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF ERCC MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ERCC6L - FOXM1	153	82	193
ERCC8 - FOXM1	870	1189	912

Table 29: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS ERCC members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 29 graphically, with the following influences - • ERCC members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > ERCC-6L/8.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ERCC members w.r.t FOXM1	
ERCC-6L/8	FOXM1

Table 30: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and ERCC members.

2.1.16. FOXM1 - FAM

Zhao et al. [37] reported higher expression levels of FAM64A in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC) tissues and cell lines. They found the existence of a physical interaction between FAM64A and FOXM1. FAM64A promoted tumorigenesis by enhancing the transcriptional activity of FOXM1, as well as by modulating FOXM1 expression via the autoregulation loop. Fu et al. [38] found that FAM72A is a cell-cycle-regulated gene that is transcriptionally and post-transcriptionally regulated by FOXM1 and APC/C, respectively. Study by Fei et al. [39], revealed that FAM83A hijacked the promoter of FOXM1 to progress the malignant lung adenocarcinoma (LUAD), and uncovered that the function of FAM83A is partly dependent on FOXM1 regulation. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these FAM members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FAM members along with FOXM1.

Table 31 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 32 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 31. The table 31 shows rankings of FAM members w.r.t FOXM1. FAM83D - FOXM1

shows low ranking of 3 (laplace), 130 (linear) and 515 (rbf). FAM111B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 39 (laplace), 143 (linear) and 93 (rbf). FAM72D - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 79 (laplace), 208 (linear) and 139 (rbf). FAM201A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 304 (laplace), 389 (linear) and 729 (rbf). FAM169A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 312 (laplace), 267 (linear) and 210 (rbf). FAM96AP2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 320 (laplace), 875 (linear) and 658 (rbf). FAM216A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 348 (laplace), 538 (linear) and 617 (rbf). FAM120C - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 361 (laplace), 218 (linear) and 413 (rbf). FAM161A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 564 (laplace), 9 (linear) and 243 (rbf). FAM227A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 568 (laplace), 490 (linear) and 351 (rbf). FAM72A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 673 (laplace), 586 (linear) and 597 (rbf). FAM131B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 832 (laplace), 956 (linear) and 664 (rbf). FAM81A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 918 (laplace), 155 (linear) and 403 (rbf). FAM210B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1148 (laplace), 457 (linear) and 1153 (rbf). FAM96A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1449 (laplace), 1158 (linear) and 1213 (rbf). FAM98B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1474 (laplace), 812 (linear) and 670 (rbf). FAM86JP - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1408 (linear) and 1297 (rbf). FAM168A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1182 (linear) and 835 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, FAM86A, FAM89A, FAM86C2P, FAM185A, FAM221A, FAM122B, FAM117A, FAM86B1, FAM208B, FAM173B, FAM117B, FAM86C1, FAM98A, FAM136A, FAM149B1 and FAM178A showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING FAM MEMBERS VS FOXM1							
RANKING OF FAM MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
FAM83D - FOXM1	3	130	515	FAM111B - FOXM1	39	143	93
FAM72D - FOXM1	79	208	139	FAM201A - FOXM1	304	389	729
FAM169A - FOXM1	312	267	210	FAM96AP2 - FOXM1	320	875	658
FAM216A - FOXM1	348	538	617	FAM120C - FOXM1	361	218	413
FAM161A - FOXM1	564	9	243	FAM227A - FOXM1	568	490	351
FAM72A - FOXM1	673	586	597	FAM131B - FOXM1	832	956	664
FAM81A - FOXM1	918	155	403	FAM86A - FOXM1	967	2469	1994
FAM210B - FOXM1	1148	457	1153	FAM96A - FOXM1	1449	1158	1213
FAM98B - FOXM1	1474	812	670	FAM89A - FOXM1	1566	2115	1226
FAM86C2P - FOXM1	1615	1819	2159	FAM185A - FOXM1	1762	1617	2098
FAM221A - FOXM1	1777	1050	1634	FAM86JP - FOXM1	1881	1408	1297
FAM122B - FOXM1	1921	2502	2134	FAM117A - FOXM1	1927	1474	2423
FAM168A - FOXM1	1931	1182	835	FAM86B1 - FOXM1	2025	1108	2158
FAM208B - FOXM1	2109	1701	1841	FAM173B - FOXM1	2331	1680	2561
FAM117B - FOXM1	2332	2445	2041	FAM86C1 - FOXM1	2336	2469	2098
FAM98A - FOXM1	2534	2477	2467	FAM136A - FOXM1	2603	2691	2325
FAM149B1 - FOXM1	2668	2612	2602	FAM178A - FOXM1	2739	2302	2693

Table 31: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS FAM members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 31 graphically, with the following

influences - • FAM members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > FAM-83D / 111B / 72D / 201A / 169A / 96AP2 / 216A / 120C / 161A / 227A / 72A / 131B / 81A / 210B / 96A / 98B / 86JP / 168A.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

FAM members w.r.t FOXM1	
FAM-83D/111B/72D/201A/169A/96AP2/216A/120C/...	
161A/227A/72A/131B/81A/210B/96A/98B/86JP/168A	FOXM1

Table 32: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and FAM members.

2.1.17. FOXM1 - FANC

In nonmuscle invasive bladder cancer (NMIBC), Roh et al. [40] found that FOXM1 and FANCD2 were involved in recurrence. Their investigation showed that FOXM1 directly regulated the transcription of FANCD2 and depletion of FOXM1 resulted in DNA repair defects in the FA pathway and decreased resistance to chemotherapy. Thus, the FANCD2-associated FA pathway activation by FOXM1 is critical to drug resistance and bladder cancer recurrence. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these FANC members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FANC members along with FOXM1.

Table 33 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 34 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 33. The table 33 shows rankings of FANC members w.r.t FOXM1. FANCB - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 90 (laplace), 29 (linear) and 196 (rbf). FANCM - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 114 (laplace), 950 (linear) and 516 (rbf). FANCG - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 591 (laplace), 690 (linear) and 1136 (rbf). FANCI - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1118 (laplace) and 1467 (linear) FANCD2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1446 (laplace), 967 (linear) and 396 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, FANCF showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 33 graphically, with the following influences - • FANC members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > FANC-B/M/G/I/D2.

2.1.18. FOXM1 - FZD

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is known to develop chemoresistance, which is responsible for cancer recurrence and distal metastasis. Both DNA damage repair and stemness are related to chemoresistance. Sun et al. [41] identified FZD5 as expressed in TNBC and revealed that it contributed to TNBC cell G1/S transition, DNA replication, DNA damage repair, survival, and stemness. They show that FOXM1, which promoted

RANKING FANC MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF FANC MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FANCB - FOXM1	90	29	196
FANCM - FOXM1	114	950	516
FANCG - FOXM1	591	690	1136
FANCI - FOXM1	1118	1467	2293
FANCD2 - FOXM1	1446	967	396
FANCF - FOXM1	2484	2518	1900

Table 33: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS FANC members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
FANC members w.r.t FOXM1	
FANC-B/M/G/I/D2	FOXM1

Table 34: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and FANC members.

BRCA1 and BIRC5 transcription, acted as a downstream effector of FZD5 signaling. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these FZD members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FZD members along with FOXM1.

Table 35 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 36 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 35. The table 35 shows rankings of FZD members w.r.t FOXM1. FZD3 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 590 (laplace), 940 (linear) and 1481 (rbf). FZD7 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 974 (laplace), 470 (linear) and 1215 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 35 graphically, with the following influences - • FZD members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > FZD-3/7.

RANKING FZD MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF FZD MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FZD3 - FOXM1	590	940	1481
FZD7 - FOXM1	974	470	1215

Table 35: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS FZD members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
FZD members w.r.t FOXM1	
FZD-3/7	FOXM1

Table 36: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and FZD members.

2.1.19. FOXM1 - HMG

Zanin et al. [42] discovered FOXM1 as a molecular partner of HMGA1 in regulating a gene network implicated in breast cancer hallmarks. They observed that HMGA1 formed a complex with FOXM1 and stabilized it in the nucleus, thus increasing its transcriptional activity on common target genes. Further, they demonstrated that HMGA1 and FOXM1 synergistically drove breast cancer cells to promote tumor angiogenesis both in vitro in endothelial cells and in vivo in a zebrafish xenograft model. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these HMG members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these HMG members along with FOXM1.

Table 37 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 38 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 37. The table 37 shows rankings of HMG members w.r.t FOXM1. HMGN5 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 37 (laplace), 381 (linear) and 170 (rbf). HMGN3 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 148 (laplace), 89 (linear) and 87 (rbf). HMGB2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 481 (laplace), 415 (linear) and 282 (rbf). HMGN2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 957 (laplace), 1151 (linear) and 529 (rbf). HMGB3 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1224 (laplace), 1064 (linear) and 1149 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HMGB1 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING HMG MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF HMG MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
HMG N5 - FOXM1	37	381	170
HMG N3 - FOXM1	148	89	87
HMG B2 - FOXM1	481	415	282
HMG N2 - FOXM1	957	1151	529
HMG B3 - FOXM1	1224	1064	1149
HMG B1 - FOXM1	1606	1493	2133

Table 37: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS HMG members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 37 graphically, with the following influences - • HMG members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > HMG-N5/N3/B2/N2/B3.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
HMG members w.r.t FOXM1	
HMG-N5/N3/B2/N2/B3	FOXM1

Table 38: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and HMG members.

2.1.20. FOXM1 - HNRNP

Cervical cancer (CCa) patients with lymph node (LN) metastasis face poor prognoses. Aberrant N6-methyladenosine (m⁶A) modification of RNAs are known to promote tumor metastasis, but their role in CCa remains unclear. Study by Liu et al. [43] revealed that HNRNPC increased tumor-related variants through m⁶A-dependent manner, thereby promoting lymphatic metastasis in CCa. They observed that HNRNPC regulated exon skipping of FOXM1 by binding to its m⁶A-modified motif and mutating the m⁶A site on FOXM1 weakened the interaction between HNRNPC and FOXM1 pre-RNA, thus leading to reduction in metastasis-related FOXM1-S variant. Similarly, results by Jiang et al. [44] suggested that the RNA-binding protein HNRNPD promoted chondrocyte senescence in the pathology of osteoarthritis (OA) by upregulating FOXM1. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-

1922159, these HNRNP members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these HNRNP members along with FOXM1.

Table 39 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 40 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 39. The table 39 shows rankings of HNRNP members w.r.t FOXM1. HNRNPNA1L2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 505 (laplace), 702 (linear) and 543 (rbf). HNRNPNA1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1163 (laplace) and 945 (rbf). HNRNPNM - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1570 (linear) and 1377 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HNRNPNR, HNRNPNC, HNRNPNA0, HNRNPNH3, HNRNPND and HNRNPNA3 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING HNRNP MEMBERS VS FOXM1

RANKING OF HNRNP MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1	laplace	linear	rbf
HNRNPNA1L2 - FOXM1	505	702	543
HNRNPNA1 - FOXM1	1163	1697	945
HNRNPNM - FOXM1	1653	1570	1377
HNRNPNR - FOXM1	1967	2684	2596
HNRNPNC - FOXM1	2289	2715	2391
HNRNPNA0 - FOXM1	2317	1802	2519
HNRNPNH3 - FOXM1	2586	2723	2005
HNRNPND - FOXM1	2666	2401	2739
HNRNPNA3 - FOXM1	2683	2663	1150

Table 39: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS HNRNP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 39 graphically, with the following influences - • HNRNP members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > HNRNPN-A1L2/A1/M.

2.1.21. FOXM1 - HSP

HSP70, together with the BAG3 and CHIP cochaperones, regulates the FOXM1 signaling pathway and Alimardan et al. [45] provide a review on HSP70, HSP90, and FOXM1 structure and function, their inhibitors and the known HSP70 cochaperones.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES
HNRNP members w.r.t FOXM1
HNRNPN-A1L2/A1/M **FOXM1**

Table 40: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and HNRNP members.

HSP and FOXM1 play significant roles in carcinogenesis. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these HSP members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these HSP members along with FOXM1.

Table 41 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 42 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 41. The table 41 shows rankings of HSP members w.r.t FOXM1. HSPB6 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 241 (laplace), 384 (linear) and 217 (rbf). HSPA4L - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 637 (laplace) and 1116 (linear) HSPE1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 700 (laplace), 1497 (linear) and 869 (rbf). HSPD1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1047 (laplace), 1555 (linear) and 176 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HSPA9 and HSPA4 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING HSP MEMBERS VS FOXM1

RANKING OF HSP MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1

	laplace	linear	rbf
HSPB6 - FOXM1	241	384	217
HSPA4L - FOXM1	637	1116	1693
HSPE1 - FOXM1	700	1497	869
HSPD1 - FOXM1	1047	1555	176
HSPA9 - FOXM1	1661	997	1965
HSPA4 - FOXM1	2687	2298	2109

Table 41: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS HSP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 41 graphically, with the following influences - • HSP members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > HSP-B6/A4L/E1/D1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES
HSP members w.r.t FOXM1
HSP-B6/A4L/E1/D1 FOXM1

Table 42: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and HSP members.

2.1.22. FOXM1 - KIF

The malignant characteristics of clear cell renal cell carcinoma (ccRCC) cells can be suppressed by inhibiting FOXM1 and KIF20A, as demonstrated by in vitro experiments, conducted by Fang et al. [46]. They found that FOXM1 can upregulate KIF20A which further activate EMT signaling. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these KIF members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these KIF members along with FOXM1.

Table 43 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 44 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 43. The table 43 shows rankings of KIF members w.r.t FOXM1. KIFC1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 24 (laplace), 177 (linear) and 503 (rbf). KIF14 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 32 (laplace), 241 (linear) and 83 (rbf). KIF18A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 53 (laplace), 349 (linear) and 438 (rbf). KIF20A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 65 (laplace), 330 (linear) and 51 (rbf). KIF2C - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 72 (laplace), 254 (linear) and 46 (rbf). KIF18B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 86 (laplace), 170 (linear) and 14 (rbf). KIF15 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 104 (laplace), 8 (linear) and 64 (rbf). KIF23 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 125 (laplace), 74 (linear) and 172 (rbf). KIF22 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 128 (laplace), 767 (linear) and 732 (rbf). KIF20B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 137 (laplace), 411 (linear) and 605 (rbf). KIF4A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 141 (laplace), 235 (linear) and 147 (rbf). KIF11 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 270 (laplace), 78 (linear) and 56 (rbf). KIF7 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 321 (laplace), 1172 (linear) and 965 (rbf). KIF9 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 633 (laplace) and 1022 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, KIF27 and KIF13A showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 43 graphically, with the following influences - ● KIF members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 → KIF-C1 / 14 / 18A / 20A / 2C / 18B / 15 / 23 / 22 / 20B / 4A / 11 / 7 / 9.

RANKING KIF MEMBERS VS FOXM1								
RANKING OF KIF MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1								
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
KIFC1 - FOXM1	24	177	503	KIF14 - FOXM1	32	241	83	
KIF18A - FOXM1	53	349	438	KIF20A - FOXM1	65	330	51	
KIF2C - FOXM1	72	254	46	KIF18B - FOXM1	86	170	14	
KIF15 - FOXM1	104	8	64	KIF23 - FOXM1	125	74	172	
KIF22 - FOXM1	128	767	732	KIF20B - FOXM1	137	411	605	
KIF4A - FOXM1	141	235	147	KIF11 - FOXM1	270	78	56	
KIF7 - FOXM1	321	1172	965	KIF9 - FOXM1	633	1823	1022	
KIF27 - FOXM1	1539	1830	2175	KIF13A - FOXM1	2407	2471	1068	

Table 43: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS KIF members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

KIF members w.r.t FOXM1	
KIF-C1/14/18A/20A/2C/18B/15/23/22/20B/4A/11/7/9	FOXM1

Table 44: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and KIF members.

2.1.23. FOXM1 - LINC

In oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), Niinuma et al. [47] showed that LINC02154 knockdown led to cell cycle arrest and apoptosis, and significantly attenuated tumor growth in vitro and in vivo. This knockdown further downregulated FOXM1. Of importance was the interaction of HNRNPK with LINC02154, which stabilized FOXM1 expression by interacting with the 3'-UTR of FOXM1 mRNA, thereby suggesting that LINC02154 and HNRNPK promote cell cycling by regulating FOXM1 expression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these LINC members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these LINC members along with FOXM1.

Table 45 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 46 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 45. The table 45 shows rankings of LINC members w.r.t FOXM1. LINC00242 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 63 (laplace), 703 (linear) and 593 (rbf). LINC00888 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 163 (laplace), 583 (linear) and 473 (rbf). LINC00261 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 231 (laplace), 298 (linear) and 50 (rbf). LINC00858 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1251 (laplace), 1208 (linear) and 813 (rbf). LINC01106 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1265 (laplace) and 849 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, LINC00338 and LINC01123 showed high ranking and might not be syn-

ergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING LINC MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF LINC MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
LINC00242 - FOXM1	63	703	593
LINC00888 - FOXM1	163	583	473
LINC00261 - FOXM1	231	298	50
LINC00858 - FOXM1	1251	1208	813
LINC01106 - FOXM1	1265	2089	849
LINC00338 - FOXM1	1593	709	1902
LINC01123 - FOXM1	1614	2332	1589

Table 45: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS LINC members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 45 graphically, with the following influences - • LINC members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > LINC-00242/00888/00261/00858/01106.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
LINC members w.r.t FOXM1	
LINC-00242/00888/00261/00858/01106	FOXM1

Table 46: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and LINC members.

2.1.24. FOXM1 - METTL

In lung adenocarcinoma (LUAD) Peng et al. [48], found that METTL1 was upregulated and via the m7G-dependent manner, it improved the RNA stability of FOXM1, leading to the up-regulation of FOXM1 which transcriptionally suppressed PTPN13 expression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these METTL members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these METTL members along with FOXM1.

Table 47 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 48 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 47.

The table 47 shows rankings of METTL members w.r.t FOXM1. METTL1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 356 (laplace), 790 (linear) and 160 (rbf). METTL13 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 719 (laplace) and 827 (linear). METTL21B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1010 (laplace) and 1079 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, METTL21A, METTL12, METTL3, METTL8, METTL16, METTL5, METTL17 and METTL2B showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING METTL MEMBERS VS FOXM1							
RANKING OF METTL MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
METTL1 - FOXM1	356	790	160	METTL13 - FOXM1	719	827	1989
METTL21B - FOXM1	1010	1990	1079	METTL21A - FOXM1	1434	2342	2542
METTL12 - FOXM1	1608	1516	2224	METTL3 - FOXM1	2060	2574	1887
METTL8 - FOXM1	2168	2150	1144	METTL16 - FOXM1	2381	1469	1791
METTL5 - FOXM1	2478	2060	2320	METTL17 - FOXM1	2546	2614	2405
METTL2B - FOXM1	2574	2509	2574				

Table 47: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS METTL members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 47 graphically, with the following influences - • METTL members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > METTL-1/13/21B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

METTL members w.r.t FOXM1

METTL-1/13/21B
FOXM1

Table 48: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and METTL members.

2.1.25. FOXM1 - MRPL

In LUAD, Zhang et al. [49] showed that MRPL51 knockdown suppressed cell proliferation, induced G1 phase arrest and decreased cell invasion. Further, it was transcriptionally activated by FOXM1 in LUAD and contributed to the malignant behaviors of tumor cells, including EMT, cell cycle progression and invasion. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these MRPL members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these MRPL members along with FOXM1.

Table 49 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 50 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 49.

The table 49 shows rankings of MRPL members w.r.t FOXM1. MRPL16 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 331 (laplace), 1087 (linear) and 606 (rbf). MRPL4 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1090 (laplace) and 1439 (rbf). MRPL11 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1117 (laplace), 444 (linear) and 983 (rbf). MRPL32 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1274 (laplace) and 998 (rbf). MRPL36 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1297 (laplace), 1014 (linear) and 997 (rbf). MRPL35 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1317 (laplace) and 1014 (rbf). MRPL3 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 236 (linear) and 806 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, MRPL37, MRPL1, MRPL45, MRPL18, MRPL13, MRPL2, MRPL34, MRPL21, MRPL17, MRPL24, MRPL9, MRPL19, MRPL48, MRPL42, MRPL51, MRPL40, MRPL50, MRPL47 and MRPL22 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

RANKING MRPL MEMBERS VS FOXM1							
RANKING OF MRPL MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
MRPL16 - FOXM1	331	1087	606	MRPL4 - FOXM1	1090	1718	1439
MRPL11 - FOXM1	1117	444	983	MRPL32 - FOXM1	1274	2630	998
MRPL36 - FOXM1	1297	1014	997	MRPL35 - FOXM1	1317	2243	1014
MRPL37 - FOXM1	1496	2455	2254	MRPL1 - FOXM1	1527	1778	2466
MRPL45 - FOXM1	1581	2658	2208	MRPL18 - FOXM1	1590	2395	2344
MRPL3 - FOXM1	1618	236	806	MRPL13 - FOXM1	1803	860	1935
MRPL2 - FOXM1	1811	1373	2652	MRPL34 - FOXM1	1825	2143	882
MRPL21 - FOXM1	1842	1956	1942	MRPL17 - FOXM1	1866	1430	2100
MRPL24 - FOXM1	1872	2377	819	MRPL9 - FOXM1	1924	1801	2685
MRPL19 - FOXM1	2226	1852	2017	MRPL48 - FOXM1	2248	2255	1992
MRPL42 - FOXM1	2414	885	2553	MRPL51 - FOXM1	2440	2465	1939
MRPL40 - FOXM1	2464	2326	2099	MRPL50 - FOXM1	2533	2095	1669
MRPL47 - FOXM1	2645	2653	2656	MRPL22 - FOXM1	2657	2522	2732

Table 49: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS MRPL members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 49 graphically, with the following influences - • MRPL members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > MRPL-16/4/11/32/36/35/3.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

MRPL members w.r.t FOXM1

MRPL-16/4/11/32/36/35/3
FOXM1

Table 50: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and MRPL members.

2.1.26. FOXM1 - PLK

In LUAD, Xu et al. [50] showed that PLK1 phosphorylates FOXM1 at Ser25, thus acquiring the reprogramming ability to stimulate the invasive traits in cancer and influence immune cell plasticity. This invasive form of p-FOXM1 upregulates the expression of IL1A/1B, VEGFA, and IL6 by direct activation, recruiting monocytes and promoting the polarization of M2d-like tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs). These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these PLK members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these PLK members along with FOXM1.

Table 51 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 52 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 51. The table 51 shows rankings of PLK members w.r.t FOXM1. PLK4 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 506 (laplace), 253 (linear) and 258 (rbf). PLK1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1108 (laplace), 1082 (linear) and 1007 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING PLK MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF PLK MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
PLK4 - FOXM1	506	253	258
PLK1 - FOXM1	1108	1082	1007

Table 51: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS PLK members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 51 graphically, with the following influences - • PLK members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > PLK-4/1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
PLK members w.r.t FOXM1	
PLK-4/1	FOXM1

Table 52: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and PLK members.

2.1.27. FOXM1 - POL/POLR

In LUAD, Ni et al. [51] showed that berberine, a natural anticancer drug, interfered the expression of survival related gene POLE2 in DNA replication mediated by FOXM1. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these POL members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these POL members along with FOXM1. Additionally, I also generated rankings of members of POLR to see if there was synergy between them and FOXM1.

Table 53 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 54 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 53. The table 53 shows rankings of POL members w.r.t FOXM1. POLQ - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 16 (laplace), 11 (linear) and 136 (rbf). POLE2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 131 (laplace), 801 (linear) and 533 (rbf). POLA1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 593 (laplace), 771 (linear) and 82 (rbf). POLG2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 749 (laplace), 1396 (linear) and 831 (rbf). POLD1 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 753 (laplace), 409 (linear) and 611 (rbf). POLD2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1052 (laplace) and 435 (rbf). POLR3K - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 609 (laplace), 868 (linear) and 493 (rbf). POLR1C - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 845 (laplace), 850 (linear) and 1218 (rbf). POLR2G - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1147 (laplace), 1074 (linear) and 1739 POLR1B - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1401 (laplace), 705 (linear) and 673 (rbf). POLR1A - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1022 (linear) and 1188 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, POLE3, POLA2, POLB, POLR1E, POLR3E, POLR2D, POLR2F, POLR1D, POLR3A and POLR2K showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 53 graphically, with the following influences - • POL members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 \rightarrow POL-Q/E2/A1/G2/D1/D2 and • POLR members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 \rightarrow POLR-3K/1C/2G/1B/1A.

2.1.28. FOXM1 - STIL/SF3

In hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), Zhang et al. [52] showed that an interaction between STIL and FOXM1 regulated the SF3A3 expression. Knockdown of FOXM1 further enhanced the anti-tumor effects of STIL loss on HCC cells in vitro and in vivo, whereas SF3A3 overexpression overturned the impact of STIL loss on HCC cells in vitro and in vivo. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these STIL-SF3 members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these STIL-SF3 members along with FOXM1. Additionally, I also generated rankings of members of STIL-SF3R to see if there was synergy between them and FOXM1.

Table 55 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored

RANKING POL MEMBERS VS FOXM1								
RANKING OF POL MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1								
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
POLQ - FOXM1	16	11	136	POLE2 - FOXM1	131	801	533	
POLA1 - FOXM1	593	771	82	POLG2 - FOXM1	749	1396	831	
POLD1 - FOXM1	753	409	611	POLE3 - FOXM1	943	1837	1718	
POLD2 - FOXM1	1052	1747	435	POLA2 - FOXM1	1605	1786	1212	
POLB - FOXM1	2333	2396	1650					
RANKING POLR MEMBERS VS FOXM1								
RANKING OF POLR MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1								
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
POLR3K - FOXM1	609	868	493	POLR1C - FOXM1	845	850	1218	
POLR2G - FOXM1	1147	1074	1739	POLR1B - FOXM1	1401	705	673	
POLR1E - FOXM1	1537	1649	1655	POLR1A - FOXM1	1712	1022	1188	
POLR3E - FOXM1	2000	1569	2497	POLR2D - FOXM1	2037	1127	1998	
POLR2F - FOXM1	2194	2488	1691	POLR1D - FOXM1	2367	2734	2534	
POLR3A - FOXM1	2485	2378	2476	POLR2K - FOXM1	2486	2698	2389	

Table 53: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS POL members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
POL members w.r.t FOXM1	
POL-Q/E2/A1/G2/D1/D2	FOXM1
POLR members w.r.t FOXM1	
POLR-3K/1C/2G/1B/1A	FOXM1

Table 54: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and POL members.

combinatorial hypotheses in table 56 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 55. The table 55 shows rankings of STIL-SF3 members w.r.t FOXM1. SF3A3 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1138 (laplace) and 809 (linear). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, STIL, SF3B3 and SF3B5 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 55 graphically, with the following influences - • SF3 members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > SF3-A3.

2.1.29. FOXM1 - USP/ITG

Integrins play critical roles in connecting the extracellular matrix and actin. Liu et al. [53] showed that USP22 was essential in maintaining breast cancer cell stemness by

RANKING STIL-SF3 MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF STIL-SF3 MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
STIL - FOXM1	2496	2688	2601
SF3A3 - FOXM1	1138	809	2103
SF3B3 - FOXM1	1310	2447	2338
SF3B5 - FOXM1	2662	2085	2023

Table 55: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS STIL-SF3 members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
STIL-SF3 members w.r.t FOXM1	
SF3-A3	FOXM1

Table 56: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and STIL-SF3 members.

promoting the transcription of integrin $\beta 1$ (ITGB1). USP22 functions as a deubiquitinase to protect the proteasomal degradation of FOXM1, a transcription factor for tumoral ITGB1 gene transcription. Immunohistochemistry staining detected a positive correlation among USP22, FOXM1, and integrin $\beta 1$ in human breast cancers. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these USP-ITG members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these USP-ITG members along with FOXM1.

Table 57 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 58 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 57. The table 57 shows rankings of USP-ITG members w.r.t FOXM1. USP13 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 485 (laplace), 153 (linear) and 70 (rbf). USP28 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1080 (linear) and 1354 (rbf). ITGA9 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 197 (laplace), 338 (linear) and 496 (rbf). ITGB3BP - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 373 (laplace), 658 (linear) and 374 (rbf). ITGAE - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1334 (laplace), and 1113 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, USP1, USP10, USP36 and USP39 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 57 graphically, with the following influences - • USP members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > USP-13/28 and • ITG

RANKING USP MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF USP MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
USP13 - FOXM1	485	153	70
USP28 - FOXM1	1741	1080	1354
USP1 - FOXM1	2035	1595	2525
USP10 - FOXM1	2049	2695	2734
USP36 - FOXM1	2463	2363	2084
USP39 - FOXM1	2550	2720	2728

RANKING ITG MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF ITG MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ITGA9 - FOXM1	197	338	496
ITGB3BP - FOXM1	373	658	374
ITGAE - FOXM1	1334	1691	1113

Table 57: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS USP-ITG members.

members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > ITG-A9/B3BP/AE.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
USP members w.r.t FOXM1	
USP-13/28	FOXM1
ITG members w.r.t FOXM1	
ITG-A9/B3BP/AE	FOXM1

Table 58: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and USP-ITG members.

2.1.30. FOXM1 - ZIC/UBE2

In ccRCC, Lv et al. [54] ZIC2 was upregulated while knockdown of ZIC2 resulted in reduced cell proliferation, invasion, migration, induction of G2/M phase arrest, and reduced tumor formation and lung metastasis in nude mice. Further, hypomethylation and high H3K4Me3 in the promoter region, and positive transcriptional regulation by FOXM1, caused high expression of ZIC2. This ZIC2 transcriptase-positively regulated UBE2C and activated AKT/mTOR signaling pathway to promote tumor malignant progression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with FOXM1. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ZIC-UBE2 members, and FOXM1, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these ZIC-UBE2 members along with FOXM1.

Table 59 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 60 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 59. The table 59 shows rankings of ZIC-UBE2-ITG members w.r.t FOXM1. ZIC2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1109 (laplace) and 260 (rbf). UBE2C - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 15 (laplace), 97 (linear) and 278 (rbf). UBE2T - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 418 (laplace), 83 (linear) and 393 (rbf). UBE2S - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 917 (laplace) and 989 (linear). UBE2G2 - FOXM1 shows low ranking of 1242 (laplace) and 714 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, ZIC5 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with FOXM1, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 59 graphically, with the following influences - • ZIC members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > ZIC-2 and • ITG members w.r.t FOXM1 with FOXM1 – > UBE2-C/T/S/G2.

3. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic FOXM1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of FOXM1-X that might be prevalent in CRC cells after treatment with ETC-1922159 drug.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

RANKING ZIC MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF ZIC MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ZIC2 - FOXM1	1109	1993	260
ZIC5 - FOXM1	1929	2588	1647
RANKING UBE2 MEMBERS VS FOXM1			
RANKING OF UBE2 MEMBERS W.R.T FOXM1			
	laplace	linear	rbf
UBE2C - FOXM1	15	97	278
UBE2T - FOXM1	418	83	393
UBE2S - FOXM1	917	989	1875
UBE2G2 - FOXM1	1242	1521	714

Table 59: 2nd order interaction ranking between FOXM1 VS ZIC-UBE2 members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ZIC members w.r.t FOXM1	
ZIC-2	FOXM1
UBE2 members w.r.t FOXM1	
UBE2-C/T/S/G2	FOXM1

Table 60: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FOXM1 and ZIC-UBE2-ITG members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Madan et al. [55].

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